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Rare Earth Metal Chelates of Isoxazoles— A Potentiometric Study

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IN continuation of our earlier work¹ wherein we had reported the stability constants of 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl isoxazole with some bivalent metal ions, we are reporting here the stability constants of the metal chelates of 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl, 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-*p*-chlorophenyl and 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-*p*-methoxyphenyl isoxazole with some rare earth metal ions in 75% v/v methanol—water mixture at 35° and an ionic strength of 0.1M KNO₃ employing Calvin-Wilson method².

Experimental

The ligands used in the present investigations have been prepared by the literature method³ and their solutions are prepared in 100% methanol. The stock solutions of the alkali and the metal ions have been prepared and estimated as outlined in our earlier paper¹. A digital pH meter-Elico Model LI-120 with a combined glass and calomel electrode assembly was employed to determine the pH changes during the titrations. The following sets of solutions were prepared and titrated against 0.1M NaOH at 35°.

(i) 5 ml 0.1M HNO₃ + 4.5 ml 1M KNO₃ + 37.5 ml CH₃OH + 3 ml H₂O.

(ii) 5 ml 0.1M HNO₃ + 4.5 ml 1M KNO₃ + 5 ml 0.01M ligand in 100% methanol + 32.5 ml CH₃OH + 3 ml H₂O.

(iii) 5 ml 0.1M HNO₃ + 4.5 ml 1M KNO₃ + 5 ml 0.01M ligand in 100% methanol + 32.5 ml methanol + 0.1 ml 0.1M metal ion solution + 2.9 ml H₂O.

In all the titrations, the volume and the ionic strength is kept constant. The pH values obtained in 75% v/v of methanol—water mixture were corrected by using the method of Van Uitert and Hass⁴. The correction factor in the aquo-organic mixture is -0.12.

Results and Discussion

3-(*o*-Hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl isoxazole (HL) is a weak acid due to the presence of *o*-hydroxyphenyl group at the 3 position of isoxazole. The dissociation of this ligand takes place in the following manner:

Proton ligand curves were obtained by plotting the degree of formation ($\bar{n}_H$) of the proton complex against pH value using the relationship derived by Irving-Rossotti⁵. The pK_a values of these ligands were obtained at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and are given in Table 1.

To study the effect of the substituent at 5-position on the dissociation of the ligand, the experiments were carried out with 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-*p*-chlorophenyl isoxazole and 3-(*o*-hydroxyphenyl)-5-*p*-methoxy isoxazoles. The presence of Cl in the 5 position causes the electron deficiency on the nitrogen atom as a result, the hydrogen bond present between N of isoxazole moiety and H of the OH group becomes weaker when compared to the unsubstituted compound. This helps in the easy liberation of proton in solution, thereby the pK_a of the compound decreases. While -OCH₃ being electron repelling group, it enhances the electron density on the nitrogen atom resulting in the strong hydrogen bonding thereby the pK_a of the compound increases. The formation curves were then obtained by plotting the degree of formation of the chelate ($\bar{n}$) against the negative logarithm of concentration of the non-protonated ligand (pL). The formation curves for these metal ligand systems obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ versus pL do not show significant flattening at $\bar{n}=1$ indicating that the spreading factor is low, the values of $\log K_1$ at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and $\log K_2$ at $\bar{n}=1.5$ obtained are therefore approximate. The stepwise formation constants have therefore been determined by the least square method⁶ and are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 35°C AND IONIC STRENGTH 0.1M KNO₃

Metal ions	3-(<i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl)-5-phenyl isoxazole			3-(<i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl)-5- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl isoxazole			3-(<i>o</i> -hydroxyphenyl)-5- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl isoxazole		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β	log K ₁	log K ₂	log β
[H ⁺]	10.25	—	—	10.30	—	—	9.80	—	—
Ce ³⁺	—	—	—	6.8062	6.0511	12.8573	5.8092	5.2542	11.0634
Pr ³⁺	7.3771	6.8185	14.1956	7.2888	7.1584	14.4472	5.9411	5.4989	11.4400
Nd ³⁺	7.4424	6.9097	14.3521	7.3948	7.1496	14.5441	5.9542	5.6893	11.6435
Sm ³⁺	7.5250	7.3197	14.8447	7.5185	7.1805	14.6990	6.4064	6.0607	12.4771
Gd ³⁺	7.8142	7.3208	15.1350	7.3979	7.1245	14.5224	6.4064	6.0607	12.4771
Dy ³⁺	8.0645	7.7806	15.8451	7.6081	7.3175	14.9206	7.1139	6.7312	13.8400

It is evident from Table 1, that the order of stability of the metal chelates of all the ligands used with different rare earth metal ions were Dy³⁺ > Gd³⁺ > Sm³⁺ > Nd³⁺ > Pr³⁺ > Ce³⁺. The stability of the metal chelates increases with decrease in ionic radii. This may be due to varying degree of stabilisation arising out of interaction of 4f metal orbitals with the ligand field.

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A Method of Preparation of Copper Hydroxylapatite and its Solid Solutions with Arsenate

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COPPER hydroxylapatite (CuHA), Cu₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH)₂ is one of the very important compounds among the apatite series. It undergoes a series of cationic and anionic exchange reactions¹. Phosphate-arsenate exchange results in the formation of a series of solid solutions of copper

hydroxylapatite with arsenate according to the following equation :

Earlier methods of preparation solid solutions of CuHA with arsenate by the solid state reaction² were however found to be discontinuous and non-homogeneous. The present work is an attempt to prepare samples of these homogeneous solid solutions over the entire compositional range by the method of co-precipitation in aqueous media. Similar studies on Ca²⁺→Cu²⁺ exchange in hydroxylapatite were reported earlier³.

Experimental

Chemicals used for preparation of samples were either AR (BDH) or E. Merck (extra pure) grade. Samples were prepared by precipitation in CO₂-free atmosphere at 37 ± 0.5° by simultaneous dropwise addition of stoichiometric quantities of copper nitrate solution and a solution containing PO₄³⁻ and AsO₄³⁻ ions in the proportion desired for solid solution. All solutions were prepared separately in carbon dioxide free doubly distilled water and pH of these solutions were maintained above 11 by the addition of excess of liquor ammonia. Then a part of copper nitrate solution was taken in a 2L flask with a side tube fitted with a three-hole rubber stopper carrying two separating funnels through two holes and a delivery tube through the third hole. Both the solutions were taken separately in the separating funnels and were allowed to drop simultaneously into the flask. CO₂-free air was continuously bubbled which kept medium of precipitation well stirred. Precipitate alongwith mother liquor was aged by boiling under reflux for 30 min. to improve homogeneity and crystallinity of precipitate. Maintenance of desired pH during preparation was ensured by testing the filtrate after separation of the precipitate since any alteration of pH of the medium during precipitation leads to the formation of copper deficient apatites.

Samples dried at 100° for few hours were analysed complexometrically⁴ and their molar volumes were determined⁵.

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